

The Impact of Cigarette Smoking on the Risk of Developing Different Types of Lung Cancer, taking into account gender: A case-series study

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Abstract

Background: Lung cancer (LC) is the second most common malignancy and a major health concern, with a high fatality rate. However, non-smoking-related lung cancer (NSRLC) is also substantial, accounting for roughly 20,500 fatalities and ranking as the eighth largest cause of cancer mortality. In areas with low smoking rates, NSRLC may provide information on reasons other than smoking. Our study sought to compile information from these regions in order to establish the usefulness of individuals in identifying non-smoking-related causes of lung cancer.

Methods: In this case series investigation, we collected data from 186 patients with lung cancer who attended Mashhad clinics between 2018 and 2023. The location was chosen since it serves as a referral center for numerous nations that are not linked with cigarette smoking.

Results: Adenocarcinoma was the most prevalent histological kind of lung cancer. The bulk of patients (32.8%) were in their 70s, with an average age of around 65 years. The sex ratio was 2.49 men to women. 39.2% of the patients had a history of smoking. 51.1% of men smoked, whereas 90.6% of women did not smoke.

Conclusion: More research is needed to find additional environmental risk factors, beyond smoking and genetic variables, that contribute to lung cancer.

Keywords: Lung cancer, Epidemiology, Gender, Cigarette, Adenocarcinoma, Non-smokers

Introduction

Lung cancer (LC), the world's second most common malignancy, is a serious health issue and the main cause of cancer-related death for both men and women in geographical regions with adequate epidemiological research (1). Smoking is a key risk

factor for lung cancer (LC), but it is not the only one; LC is one of Iran's top five cancers, with an increasing incidence (2). Cigarette smoking is estimated to cause 103,000 of the 127,070 lung cancer deaths (81%) in 2023, with an additional 3560 caused by second-hand smoke (3).

Nonsmoking-related lung cancer (NSRLC) is the eighth largest cause of cancer death among non-smokers, accounting for around 20,500 fatalities (1). Fortunately, as knowledge of active and passive smoking grows in industrialized nations, regulatory organizations may be interested in ways for detecting the etiology of lung cancer and enforcing bans. As a result, in addition to smoking, other diverse risk factors for LC, such as radon exposure, domestic fuel smoke, infections including tuberculosis, Human papillomavirus, and inflammatory illnesses, must be addressed (4). Thus, identifying groups that developed lung cancer without smoking may shed light on factors other than smoking for lung cancer. Younger people smoke more cigarettes, but the age at which they get lung cancer is unknown (5). Previously, it was discovered that many people with lung cancer had no smoking history. As a result, we attempted to collect data on the frequency of lung cancer among nonsmokers in an epidemiological study in order to determine the causes of lung cancer in this population (5). Lung cancer incidence in nonsmokers may be increasing, particularly in Asia. Adenocarcinoma is the most frequent kind of lung cancer in nonsmokers, and it is more likely to harbor targetable driver mutations (5). To update existing knowledge on the epidemiology of lung cancer and the impacts of smoking, this study looks at the prevalence of lung cancer in Mashhad from 2018 to 2023.

Methods

In this case-series analysis, we collected data (by convenience sampling) from 186 lung cancer patients who visited two private pulmonary and oncology clinics in Mashhad between 2018 and 2023. Electronic documentation were collected from both clinics, and patients or their families answered questionnaires in-person.

A recent study in Mashhad found that 68.5% of individuals with tracheobronchial lung cancer smoked (6).

To evaluate, we use descriptive statistics to determine the epidemiology of lung cancer and its distribution. The quantitative data was examined as Mean $\pm$ SD. The primary variables are age, gender (male vs. female), histological subtypes (adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, small cell carcinoma, etc.), and smoking status (nonsmokers vs. smokers).

Fisher's exact test and the Chi-squared test were used for comparative statistical analysis.

All statistical analyses and visual designs were carried out using SPSS v.26 software, with a significance level of 0.05.

Results

This cross-sectional study included one hundred eighty-six (186) patients with histologically confirmed lung cancer. The sex distribution included 133 males and 53 females. At diagnosis, the mean age ($\pm$ SD) was 65 ± 11.6 years, with a range of 32 to 96 years. The average age of men and women was 64.71 ± 11.18 and 66.72 ± 12.49 years, respectively, with no significant difference. The seventh and eighth decades of life have the highest population (70s (32.80%) and 80s (26.34%).

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Female smoker respondents were significantly older than male smokers (mean age = 73.4 vs. 63.63, $p = 0.016$) (see Figure 1). There was no discernible age difference between nonsmoking male and female lung cancer patients. (p -value > 0.05) (Table 1).

Table 2 contrasts the histopathological classifications among our subjects. There was no significant difference in histological types of lung cancer between nonsmokers and smokers ($p=0.318$). Among smokers, 82.2% had non-small cell lung cancer, while 17.8% had small cell lung cancer; among nonsmokers, 87.6% had non-small cell lung cancer and 12.4% had small cell lung cancer. Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference in histopathological types between smokers and nonsmokers. ($P= 0.36$).

Table 1. Smoking status and Mean age in male and female subjects suffering from lung cancer

		Smoking status				Total	
		Smoker		Non-smoker		Number	Mean age
		Number	Mean age	Number	Mean age		
Sex	Male	68	63.63±8.6	65	65.85±13.3	133	64.71 ± 11.18
	Female	5	73.4±5.6	48	66.02±12.8	53	66.72 ± 12.49
<i>Total</i>		73		113		186	65±11.6

Figure 1. Age distribution among both genders with lung cancer

Table 2. Comparison of histophysiological types of lung cancer between smoker and non-smoker groups

		Smoking		Total
		Smoker	Non-smoker	
Cancer	SCLC	17.8%	12.4%	14.5%
	SCC	24.7%	25.7%	25.3%
	Poorly-differentiated carcinoma	1.4%	0.00	0.5%
	NSCLC undifferentiated	20.5%	14.2%	16.7%
	LCC	0.00	1.8%	1.1%
	Adenocarcinoma	35.6%	46.0%	41.9%
Total		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

SCLC = Small Cell Lung Cancer, SCC = Squamous Cell Carcinoma, NSCLC = Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer, LCC = Large Cell Carcinoma

Discussion

In this investigation, we found that the sex ratio of males to girls is 2.49. Furthermore, our findings revealed that male smokers were more likely than female smokers to get lung cancer. This finding was not observed in the nonsmoking group. We also discovered no significant difference in lung cancer types between smoking and nonsmoking men and women. Our data show that more than 60% of our lung cancer patients were not smokers. The age distribution was in the seventh and eighth decades of life, indicating that there is a gender difference in the age of cancer onset, with females developing cancer in their 80s and 70s and males in their 70s and 60s, indicating a group of subjects who were not traditionally exposed to smoking. In this context, prevention of lung cancer in these populations requires research into risk factors other than cigarette smoking. Our findings show that adenocarcinoma (41.9%) is the most common kind of lung cancer, followed by SCC (25.3%), independent of smoking status. Furthermore, adenocarcinoma is the most common kind of cancer in non-smokers.

A recent global study on the sex ratio discovered that the standardized incidence rate for males to females is 2.32 (9). Numerous studies from different regions of the world have found a higher incidence of LC in men (16). Men's greater smoking rates are thought to be the primary cause of the global prevalence of lung cancer in males (10).

Some experts believe that women, even if they do not smoke, are more likely to develop lung cancer than men. Siegel and colleagues also discovered that a higher proportion of women with lung cancer were nonsmokers than males, and that women faced higher risks than men, despite smoking at comparable levels (8). Khorami and colleagues found that air pollution increases the incidence of lung cancer in nonsmokers (11). The increased prevalence of lung cancer among nonsmokers could be attributed to variables such as passive smoking, occupational exposure, estrogen effects in women, and exposure to cooking fumes and viruses (12). Non-smokers' lung cancer is on the rise and is the 11th most frequent malignancy, accounting for the seventh biggest number of cancer-related fatalities (17). Another study found that squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma were the most prevalent histological kinds of lung cancer, with males having a greater incidence than females (15). Previous research suggests that never-smokers with lung cancer are more likely to develop adenocarcinoma (6).

On the other hand, several studies have found that women had a higher chance of developing lung cancer than men, even when they smoke at comparable or higher amounts (7). Another study found that males have a higher risk of lung cancer due to their higher smoking rate (10).

In Asian countries, nonsmokers with lung cancer are younger than smokers (9). Another study in our area found no evidence of a significant prevalence of lung cancer in those with anthracofibrosis (14). The outcomes of this study deserve the attention of two groups: 1- Researchers who work in health services and assess potential environmental risk factors such as radon gas and occupational pollution; 2- Clinicians who interact with patients and should look into possible genetic causes to find a case in families with cancer patients.

One limitation of our research was the lower prevalence of female smokers in our location when compared to the global percentage of male smokers. Furthermore, occupational situations can expose people to a variety of toxins that can cause the development of some malignancies. Other factors suspected of contributing to cancer formation include radon exposure, domestic fuel smoking, infections, and inflammatory illnesses, all of which require more investigation. It is critical to examine issues other than smoking, such as the use of opioids, which are commonly inhaled in our region.

Conclusion

Lung cancer is one of Iran's five most prevalent malignancies, with an increasing incidence. It is most common in the seventh decade and has a high prevalence in men. Adenocarcinoma is the most prevalent kind in our area. Although our location has a lower rate of cigarette consumption than other research, opium inhalation is suspected to be a substantial concern. As a result, more research is needed to find additional environmental risk factors that, in addition to smoking and genetics, contribute to lung cancer.

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Conflict of interest: None of the authors had any financial conflicts of interest.

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